

OSCILLATING SPECTRA ASSOCIATED TO CERTAIN SEQUENCES

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ABSTRACT. Identities originating in the theory of symmetric functions express members of arithmetic sequences as determinants. In this setting we studied numerically sequences $\{a(n)\}_{n \geq 1}$ derived from the Fourier expansions of cusp forms. We observed that, within the range of our observations, in certain cases the spectra of matrices we attached to these sequences exhibit oscillatory behavior. We collect data on this behavior in some other sequences. We propose that sequences exhibiting oscillatory behavior may form vector spaces. We initiate testing of this proposal.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Identities ([M], Lemmas 2.1 and 2.2 below) originating in the theory of symmetric functions express members of arithmetic sequences $\{h_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ with $h_0 = 1$ as $h_n = |J_n|/n!$ for particular matrices $J_{h,n}$ where $|\cdot|$ is the determinant. We studied eigenvalues of the J_n empirically. After a procedure we will call *deformation* by a number c , the minimum modulus among the eigenvalues for the deformed matrix $J_n^{(c)}$ sometimes appears to oscillate in a nearly periodic fashion with n ; addressing the question “When?” is part of our project.

We saw the oscillatory behavior in, for example, the sequence $\{h_n\}_{n \geq 0} = \{\lambda_n\}_{n \geq 0}$ with $\lambda_0 = 1$ and $\lambda_n = \tau(p_n)$ for positive integers n , where τ is Ramanujan’s function and p_n denotes the n^{th} prime number. D. H. Lehmer showed [Le47] that, if τ has any zeros, the smallest one has the form $\lambda(n^*)$ for some n^* . In our setup, this would mean that the spectrum of $J_{\lambda,n^*}^{(c)}$ contains zero. This fact was the motivation for our article.

We should emphasize that at present we cannot say that the spectrum of J_{λ,n^*} would contain zero if $J_{\lambda,n^*}^{(c)}$ contained zero. That is also a part of this project.

We also saw the oscillatory behavior in newforms coming from elliptic curves listed in Cremona’s database, and in other cusp forms coming from spaces of higher weight and larger dimension, for which the vanishing of

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coefficients is not an issue; it is common. We also collected data on the oscillatory behavior of several sequences that do not come from modular forms.

The present article will not discuss the open questions listed above. Instead, we propose that families of sequences exhibiting oscillatory behavior may have algebraic structure, and we initiate tests of this proposal. We say that a numerical sequence $\{h_n\}_{n=0,1,\dots}$ with $h_0 = 1$ is *h-coherent* if the minimum moduli among the roots of the characteristic polynomials $\chi(J_n)$ oscillate (as certified by signal-processing tests.) We also say that an arbitrary sequence $\{f_n\}$ of polynomials over \mathbb{Q} , whether or not it occurs as a sequence of characteristic polynomials, is *f-coherent* if (a) it is the zero-sequence or if (b) the minimum moduli among the roots of the $\{f_n\}_{n=1,2,\dots}$ oscillate. We denote as V_h the set of sequences $\{h_n\}_{n>0}$ such that $\{1, h_1, h_2, \dots\}$ is *h-coherent*. (The truncation of the sequence is required by the demand in our lemmas below that $h_0 = 1$, combined with our desire to turn the *h-coherent* sequences into an additively closed set.) We write V_f for the set of *f-coherent* sequences $\{f_n\}_{n\geq 0}$. We speculate that V_f and V_h are closed under addition, with sums taken term by term and assembled into sequences. Obviously, closure of V_f under multiplication by a complex number is automatic, so it becomes a vector space over \mathbb{C} if it is additively closed. The situation for V_h in this regard is less clear, because we have yet to test whether it is closed under multiplication by scalars. At the time of the present draft, the scope of our tests of additive closure of V_f and V_h is limited, but we have not found counterexamples.

Here are several more questions that will not be addressed in the present article. Theorem 2.3 (below) enforces various relations among the coefficients of the characteristic polynomial of a J matrix. (For example, it must have leading term 1.) Let us say that *f-coherent* sequences of characteristic polynomials of J matrices are *J-coherent*. We cannot say, at present, whether our tests of V_f for additive closure are biased by the circumstance that the sequences of *f-coherent* polynomials we have for testing are mainly *J-coherent*. Also, obviously (because our tests examine finite data sets) we do not even know that V_f and V_h are non-empty, or—if V_f is non-empty—whether it contains sequences that are not *J-coherent*. If it happens that V_f or V_h is a vector space, one might also ask whether one of both of them is a metric space, a Banach space, or a Hilbert space under appropriate ℓ^2 norms, and then whether one or the other is open in some nice ambient space.

2. LEMMAS

These lemmas appear, for example, in MacDonald's book [M], but the proofs are not easy to locate; in fact, we have not located them. Home-made proofs of these statements are stored in our repository [Bre25]¹. In

¹“Lemmas for ‘Ramanujan’s function on small primes’ ”

the sequel, we denote the cardinality of a set S by $\#S$ and the determinant of a matrix M by $|M|$.

Lemma 2.1. *The equations below are equivalent. (We will refer to both of them as equation (D) in the sequel.) Let $h_0 = 1$ and*

$$(D1) \quad nh_n = \sum_{r=1}^n j_r h_{n-r}$$

for $n \geq 1$. With $H(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} h_n t^n$ and $J(t) = \sum_{r=1}^{\infty} j_r t^r$,

$$(D2) \quad t \frac{d}{dt} H(t) = H(t) J(t).$$

With f_0 possibly defined as equal to one, let \bar{j} denote the sequence $\{f_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{Z}^+}$. Let $J_n(\bar{j})$ and $H_n(\bar{h})$ be the matrices

$$\begin{pmatrix} j_1 & -1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ j_2 & j_1 & -2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ j_{n-1} & j_{n-2} & \cdots & j_1 & -n+1 \\ j_n & j_{n-1} & j_{n-2} & \cdots & j_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

and

$$\begin{pmatrix} h_1 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 2h_2 & h_1 & 1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ nh_n & h_{n-1} & h_{n-2} & \cdots & h_1 \end{pmatrix},$$

respectively.

Lemma 2.2. *Let $h_0 = j_1 = 1$. Equation (D) implies that*

$$(1) \quad j_n = (-1)^{n+1} |H_n(\bar{h})|.$$

and

$$(2) \quad n! h_n = |J_n(\bar{j})|$$

for $n \geq 1$.

Next we state a corollary of the following theorem in Vein and Dale's book [Vein1999].

Proposition 1. *(Vein and Dale, Theorem 4.23) Let $A_n =$*

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_1 & -1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ a_2 & a_1 & -2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{n-1} & a_{n-2} & \cdots & a_1 & -(n-1) \\ a_n & a_{n-1} & \cdots & a_2 & a_1 \end{pmatrix}^T,$$

where the T operator is matrix transpose. Let $B_n(x) = |A_n - xI_n|$, so that $B_n(x) = (-1)^n \chi_{A_n}(x)$. Then

$$B_n(x) = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} |A_r| x^{n-r}.$$

The corollary is the following

Theorem 2.3. ² With h and j as in the above lemmas,

$$\chi((J_n(\bar{j}))(x)) = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} r! h_r (-1)^r x^{n-r}.$$

Proof. Determinants are invariant under the transpose, so, setting each a_i equal to j_i in the lemmas above, the proposition can be restated in the following way: Let $J_n(\bar{j}) =$

$$\begin{pmatrix} j_1 & -1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ j_2 & j_1 & -2 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ j_{n-1} & j_{n-2} & \cdots & j_1 & -(n-1) \\ j_n & j_{n-1} & \cdots & j_2 & j_1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Let $C_n(x) = |(J_n(\bar{j}) - xI_n)|$, so that $C_n(x) = (-1)^n \chi((J_n(\bar{j}))(x))$. By Proposition 1, $C_n(x) =$

$$\sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} |J_r(\bar{j})| (-1)^{n-r} x^{n-r} =$$

(by Lemma 2.2)

$$\sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} r! h_r (-x)^{n-r} = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} r! h_r (-1)^{n-r} x^{n-r}.$$

Simplifying, $\chi((J_n(\bar{j}))(x)) = \sum_{r=0}^n \binom{n}{r} r! h_r (-1)^r x^{n-r}$. \square

Remark 1. This result allows us to bypass the calculation of determinants, resulting in a marked speedup, when computing the polynomials χ . So far we have applied it in Figure 2B below. Its implementation is described in Remark 3 below.

Now let M be an $n \times n$ matrix over a field. For any subset $S \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, let $M[S, S]$ denote the submatrix of M with rows and columns indexed by S . The following proposition is well known. (For example, see equation (1.2.13) in Horn and Johnson's book [Horn2012].)

²Here we are merely codifying an argument shown to us by J. López-Bonilla. See also the personal communication of Petović to the author *Petović's proof* [Bre25].

Proposition 2. *The coefficient a_k of x^k in $\chi(M)$ satisfies*

$$a_{n-k} = (-1)^k \sum_{\substack{\#S=k \\ S \subseteq \{1,2,\dots,n\}}} |M[S, S]|.$$

Remark 2. Let $h_0 = 1$ and $h_n = \tau(n)$ when n is positive. Let $\{j_n\}_{n=1,2,\dots}$ be the sequence paired with h in equation (D1) above. Now let n be positive. Then $\chi(J_n(\bar{j}))(0) = 0$ if and only if $|J_n(\bar{j})| = 0$, so, by Lemma 2.2.2, $\chi(J_n(\bar{j}))(0) = 0$ if and only if $\tau(n) = 0$. Now if $\chi(J_n(\bar{j}))$ is irreducible over the rational numbers, zero is not a root of $\chi(J_n(\bar{j}))(x)$ and $\tau(n) \neq 0$. A similar argument works if we consider the sequence for which $h_n = \lambda(n)$ when n is positive.

We will not focus on this kind of sufficient condition in the sequel. We mention it because it is the only such condition we know at the time of the present draft. Instead we explore a geometric phenomenon: under certain conditions, which so far we cannot crisply describe, the eigenvalues of “deformed” versions of the $\chi(J_n(x))$ (defined in the next section) appear to oscillate as point sets as n increases. We would like to gain control over this and use it to bound the distance of these eigenvalues away from zero for certain sequences h , then to devise a version of the argument to bound the eigenvalues of the original (“undeformed”) matrices away from zero as well. This seems to be a challenging task. What we would like to do at this stage is simply to understand what it is about the $\chi(J_n(x))$ that induces the observed oscillations (when in fact they do so.) We have collected lists of these characteristic polynomials for some sequences h (Fourier coefficients of modular forms), which are available to the interested reader in data files generated in the SageMath *Jupyter* notebooks in our repository [Bre25]. We have not found a way to predict whether the relevant plots oscillate simply from characteristics of the modular forms that they come from. We speculate that first we need to learn how to make such predictions from basic features of the characteristic polynomials.

3. DEFORMATIONS

For a sequence $S = \{x_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{Z}^+}$, let $S^{(c)} = \{c, x_1, x_2, \dots\}$, $J_n^{(c)}(\bar{j}) = J_n(\overline{j^{(c)}})$ and $H_n^{(c)}(\bar{h}) = H_n(\overline{h^{(c)}})$. We refer to them as *deformations* of the matrices $H_n(\bar{h})$ and $J_n(\bar{j})$. We will freely abuse the notation by employing the H, h, J , and j symbols to denote objects in a way that depends on the context.

Remark 3. The most straightforward workflow to find $\chi(J_n(\overline{j^{(c)}}))$ for a given member of a sequence $\{h_n^{(c)}\}_n$ may be (concisely) diagrammed as follows:

$$h_n \xrightarrow{(D1)} j_n \longrightarrow j_n^{(c)} \longrightarrow J_n^{(c)} \longrightarrow \chi(J_n(\overline{j^{(c)}})).$$

The code in most of the *Jupyter* notebooks cited in the index of the present draft follows this pattern, but in our recent experience the following workflow is more efficient.

$$h_n \xrightarrow{(D1)} j_n \longrightarrow j_n^{(c)} \xrightarrow{(D1)} h_n^{(c)} \xrightarrow{Th.2.3} \chi(J_n(\overline{j^{(c)}})).$$

(So far we have applied it only in a few figures.)

4. THE SEQUENCE $\{\lambda(n)\}$.

4.1. The sequence $\{\lambda(n)\}$ and its developments. We define a sequence \overline{j}_λ by requiring $j_\lambda(n)$ and $h_n = \lambda(n)$ together to satisfy equation (D). By Lemma 2.2 (2), $\lambda(n) = |J_{\lambda,n}(\overline{j})|/n!$. Let $\Pi_n(x) = \chi(J_{\lambda,n}(\overline{j}))(x) = |xI - J_{\lambda,n}(\overline{j})|$ be the characteristic polynomial of $J_{\lambda,n}(\overline{j})$. Plots 2, 3 and 4 show the behavior of the minimum modulus among the eigenvalues of $\Pi_n^{(c)}$ ($c = 1, 2, 3$) and Π_n respectively. They are relevant to Lehmer's question (does Ramanujan's tau function ever vanish?) because the following statements are equivalent:

- (a) $\lambda(n) = \tau(p_n) = 0$,
- (b) $|J_{\lambda,n}(\overline{j})| = 0$, and
- (c) $\Pi_n(0) = 0$.

Remark 4. Writing³ $\Pi_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n a_{n,n-k} x^{n-k}$, Theorem 2.3 gives

$$(3) \quad a_{n,n-k} = (-1)^k k! \binom{n}{k} \lambda(k).$$

Remark 5. The number of terms in the sum in Proposition 2 is $\binom{n}{k}$, so the simplest way to reconcile Proposition 2 and equation (3) is to suppose that the structural symmetries of $J_{\lambda,n}(\overline{j})$ somehow force $|J_{\lambda,n}(\overline{j})[S, S]| = (-1)^k k! \lambda(k)$ just when $S \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and $\#S = k$. But this turns out to be too good to be true.⁴ Instead, there must be systematic cancellations coming from those symmetries. So far, we have not understood these cancellations.

4.2. Characteristic functions of the deformed matrices $J_{\lambda,n}^{(c)}(\overline{j})$. Let $\chi(J_{\lambda,n}^{(c)}(\overline{j})) = \Pi_n^{(c)}(x)$ (say.) Let $E_n^{(c)}$ be the set of zeros of $\Pi_n^{(c)}(x)$ and let $\mu_n^{(c)} = \min_{v \in E_n^{(c)}} |v|$; then it appears that the graph of the pairs $(n, \mu_n^{(c)})$ lies on an oscillating curve for $1 \leq c \leq 3$ (see Figures 2, 3 and 4). As a control, we repeated the calculation for $h(n) = \tau(p_n + 1)$ for $c = 1$. Figure 6 shows the resulting plot. It shows no oscillatory behavior for this choice of h , suggesting that the choice of prime indices *per se* was decisive. (See Remark 6 below, however, for our own reservations about this argument.) The deep spikes in the lower, logarithmic plot in Figure 2A suggest that the approach of the roots of $\Pi_n^{(1)}(x)$ to the origin may behave in a predictable way, but the details are not clear to us because (among other reasons) our data is limited. We do not know the details of the relationship of the roots of

³See 'undeformed tauprime2nov25no3.ipynb' in the repository [Bre25].

⁴See 'too good.ipynb' in [Bre25].

$\Pi_n(x)$ to those of the $\Pi_n^{(c)}(x)$, so the connection, if any, to Lehmer's question is unclear.

The lower envelope of the lower plot of logarithms of minimum moduli for each n in $\{2, 3, \dots, 400\}$ displayed in Figure 3 appear to behave regularly: the abscissas of the points on the lower envelope form a set $\{5, 9, \dots, 395\}$, which, when they are replaced by their residues modulo 4, make Table 1. The size of the blocks of equal residues are 10 for the first one and 9 for each of the others.⁵

For contrast, we reproduce in Figure 7 a plot of the minimum moduli for each n for the undeformed characteristic polynomials $\Pi_n(x)$. We have not attempted the sort of analysis we just discussed for the $\Pi_n^{(1)}(x)$.

We want a global-in- c understanding of the deformed plots. After prepending c to $\overline{j_\lambda}$, denoting this deformation as $\overline{j_\lambda^{(c)}}$ and once more applying equation (D1), we computed the sequence $\overline{h_\lambda^{(c)}}$ from $\overline{j_\lambda^{(c)}}$. We formed the list of pairs $(c, n!h_\lambda^{(c)}(n))$. (These are just the values of the determinants from Lemma 2.2 in this situation; but now we bypass the determinants and gain significant time savings.) We found that, within the range of our observations, these pairs interpolate a polynomial D_n (say) of degree n . For given n , we found the minimum modulus among the roots of D_n and plotted these minima against n . In the case $c \in \mathbb{Z}^{\geq 0}$, the result was the same kind of oscillating wave form that the first few individual values of c exhibit, as we see in Figure 5.⁶

5. OSCILLATORY BEHAVIOR IN NEWFORMS FROM ELLIPTIC CURVES

Because the cusp form Δ is the generating function of the multiplicative Ramanujan function, which displays oscillatory behavior in the range of our observations, we searched a source of cusp forms that are generating functions of other multiplicative functions: Cremona's database [LMFDB] of cusp forms $\sum_n a(n)q^n$ associated to elliptic curves in virtue of the Modularity Theorem. We found similar oscillatory behavior. (But see the next section for examples of oscillatory behavior coming from cusp forms the coefficient functions of which are not multiplicative.)

The forms in Cremona's database have weight two and varying levels.⁷ In the limited range of our observations, there is much variation in the oscillatory behavior, or lack of it, in deformed curves.

⁵We are using data from the lower envelope of the logarithms of the minimum moduli. (The lower plot in Figure 3.) See "tauprime=h logarithmic envelopes prec100 n400 1dec25.ipynb" in [Bre25].

⁶See Table 7 below and notebook 'tauprime many c's 18feb26' in [Bre25]. The reader will notice that we ran the routines twice, at 64-bit and 100-bit precision. The results were indistinguishable.

⁷SageMath notebooks corresponding to Table 4 are in [Bre25].

In contrast to the inclusion of plots of the logarithms of minimum moduli among eigenvalues associated to matrices representing Ramanujan's original tau function, we omit such plots for the curves in Cremona's database. The logarithm plots in the former situation served to demonstrate that the minima were not hitting zero, but for the Cremona database curves, they must occasionally do so, because the corresponding Fourier coefficients $a(n)$ themselves occasionally vanish.

Remark 6. Among our figures we have plots of eigenvalue minimum moduli for the sequences $h(n) = a(n)$ and $h(n) = a(p_n)$, but also for the sequences $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$. Our original intention was to introduce controls like the one we described above, which was meant to provide some evidence for the thesis that the $\lambda(n) = \tau(p_n)$ were producing oscillations because of arithmetic characteristics of the inputs. We expected to see a pattern in which the sequences $h(n) = a(p_n)$ induced oscillations among the minimal eigenvalues, and the sequences $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$ did not, but there is no such pattern. This undercuts the rationale behind our original controls for $h(n) = \lambda(n)$. We have carried forward all controls into this article anyway, for obvious reasons.

6. CUSP FORMS FROM SPACES OF WEIGHT EXCEEDING TWO

We have begun to test for oscillatory behavior among cusp forms belonging to spaces of weight greater than two. Some Hecke eigenforms in such spaces have non-rational Fourier expansions. Decimal estimates of their coefficients carry error that could explode in our calculations. To avoid this issue, we examined the sums of the eigenforms over the automorphisms of their coefficient fields that fix \mathbb{Q} (the traces.) These objects have rational expansions.

To explain this, we sketch Hecke theory up to the definition of newforms. Denoting the space of cusp forms at level N and weight k as $S_k(\Gamma_0(N))$, for $f, g \in S_k(\Gamma_0(N))$ the Petersson inner product is defined as $\langle f, g \rangle =$

$$\int_{\Gamma_0(N) \backslash \mathfrak{H}} f(z) \overline{g(z)} y^k \frac{dx dy}{y^2}.$$

Let $S_k^{\text{old}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ be the subspace of all linear combinations of $f(dz)$ where $f \in S_k(\Gamma_0(M))$ for some $M|N$ with $M < N$ and $d|(N/M)$. Let $S_k^{\text{new}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ be the orthogonal complement of $S_k^{\text{old}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ with respect to the Petersson inner product. Then $S_k(\Gamma_0(N)) = S_k^{\text{old}}(\Gamma_0(N)) \oplus S_k^{\text{new}}(\Gamma_0(N))$.

Let T_1 be the identity operator on $S_k(\Gamma_0(N))$ and, for primes $p \nmid N$, let the Hecke operator T_p satisfy

$$T_p \left(\sum a_n q^n \right) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \left(a_{pn} + p^{k-1} a_{n/p} \right) q^n,$$

where $a_{n/p} = 0$ if $p \nmid n$. For $e \geq 2$, let $T_{p^e} = T_p T_{p^{e-1}} - p^{k-1} T_{p^{e-2}}$.

For prime divisors p of N , let the operator U_p satisfy

$$U_p \left(\sum a_n q^n \right) = \sum_{n \geq 1} a_{pn} q^n,$$

and set $U_{p^e} = U_p^e$ where the exponent on the right side means repeated composition. For $n = \prod_p p^{e_p}$, let $T_n = \prod_{p \nmid N} T_{p^{e_p}} \cdot \prod_{p|N} U_{p^{e_p}}$. A *newform* in $S_k^{\text{new}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ is a cusp form $f \in S_k^{\text{new}}(\Gamma_0(N))$ with $a_1(f) = 1$ that is a simultaneous eigenvector for all Hecke operators T_p for $p \nmid N$ and for all U_p such that $p \mid N$.

We consider a separate linear map to extract rational expansions from the newforms. For v in a vector space V and a linear map $\mu : V \rightarrow V$, let $\text{tr}(\mu)$ be sum of the eigenvalues of μ . For a finite extension of fields L/K viewed as a vector space over K , let $\mu_\alpha(v) = \alpha v$. We write $\text{Tr}_{L/K}(\alpha) = \text{tr}(\mu_\alpha)$ and consider a finite extension E/\mathbb{Q} such that all of the Fourier coefficients in the expansion of a newform f lie in E . E/\mathbb{Q} is separable, so we may write $E = \mathbb{Q}(\alpha)$ for some α in E by the Primitive Element Theorem. It is well known that $\text{Tr}_{E/\mathbb{Q}}(\alpha)$ is rational.⁸

In our first example, we inspected the unique-up-to-conjugacy newform f in $S_4(\Gamma_0(11))$, whose coefficient field is $\mathbb{Q}(\alpha)$ with $\alpha^2 - 2\alpha - 2 = 0$ (so $\alpha = 1 \pm \sqrt{3}$). The space has dimension 2 and a single orbit under μ_α of degree 2. We carried out our usual procedures for the sequences $h_{\text{all}}(n) = \text{Tr}_{\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{3})/\mathbb{Q}}(a_n(f))$ and $h_{\text{primes}}(n) = \text{Tr}_{\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{3})/\mathbb{Q}}(a_{p_n}(f))$, setting $h_{\text{all}}(0) = h_{\text{primes}}(0) = 1$ to conform to equation (D). The minimum-modulus eigenvalue plots for our J matrices are shown in Figure 42. The function $n \mapsto h_{\text{all}}(n)$ is not multiplicative on positive n , and this is the first such example with oscillatory behavior that we have found.

7. OTHER SEQUENCES

We do not understand the pattern of occurrences of oscillations among the minimum moduli plotted in the figures below. We have searched unsuccessfully for predictive criteria among the characteristics of the modular forms in our numerical experiments. Now we are looking for such criteria among the characteristic polynomials. We are guessing that such criteria, if there are any, will be easier to spot for sequences h that are constructed as simply as possible. As a beginning, in Figures 48 and 49 we display minimum moduli plots for the sequences $\{p_{n+1} - p_n\}_{n \geq 1}$, $\{p_{n+1} - p_n - 2\}_{n \geq 1}$, and $\{n^a\}_{n \geq 1}$, $a = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

8. TESTS OF ADDITIVE CLOSURE

Obviously the presence of oscillatory behavior, or its lack, is determined by polynomial spectra. We use Fourier analytic methods to certify the presence of this behavior. Writing code for signal analysis is not within the present writer's competence, so he relied for this on the AI model

⁸For example, combine [Orr] (Lemma 19) and [Marcus] (corollary to Theorem 4').

Claude [Anthropic2026]. The code is in our repository [Bre25] under the title “`version_9_4.py`”. A guide by Claude to the interpretation of the reports generated by this code is also stored there under the title “`v9_4_interpretation_guide.pdf`”. These reports include a significance score for the first-ranked period of the plot under consideration, which for most of our tests is 99%. But in some cases (for example, that of Chebyshev polynomials, no period passes the relevant statistical tests, yet the report summary issues the verdict “PERIODIC” on the basis of another parameter, ACF strength.

Tests of additive closure for V_f are illustrated in Figure 50. We keep track of ongoing tests of V_f closure in Table 2 and of V_h closure in Table 3. (In the code for columns of Table 2 labeled “Plot 1” and “Plot 2”, unlike the column “Sum plot”, there is no need to take an extra step to extract the list of polynomials. It is just the list of characteristic polynomials.) For the purpose of these tests, we are going to count as h - or f -coherent any sequence that is certified PERIODIC.

We now describe the work flows in the code that produced the tables. Let $E(f_n)$ be the set of zeros of a polynomial f_n and let $\mu_n = \min_{v \in E(f_n)} |v|$. The code for each plot among our figures takes as input a numerical sequence $\{h(n)\}_n$, associates to it a sequence of characteristic polynomials $\{\chi_n\}_n$ in accordance with our lemmas, and creates a list of pairs $\{(n, \mu_n)\}_n$. Finally, the list of pairs is graphed. So the work flow for a given n to generate the original figures may be sketched as follows:

$$h(n) \longrightarrow \chi_n \longrightarrow E(\chi_n) \longrightarrow \mu_n.$$

The code collects the sequences $\{\chi_n\}_n$ and $\{\chi'_n\}_n$ from earlier code that generated plots displaying oscillatory behavior in two of the figures as certified by our Fourier analyses. Because those two plots showed oscillatory behavior, $\{\chi_n\}_n$ and $\{\chi'_n\}_n$ are f -coherent by definition; this is their crucial property for Table 2. The process recorded in Table 2 tests whether or not their sum $\{\chi_n + \chi'_n\}_n$ which is not necessarily a sequence of characteristic polynomials at all, is also f -coherent. If it is, we are looking at an instance of V_f additive closure. The point of compiling Table 2 is to find out whether not we will always see additive closure in these circumstances. Any instance where we do not would refute the hypothesis that V_f is closed under addition.

The code for Table 3 collects h -coherent sequences $\{h_n\}_n$ and $\{h'_n\}_n$ from earlier code that generated plots displaying oscillatory behavior in two of our figures, as certified by our Fourier analyses. It forms a third sequence $\{h_n + h'_n\}_n =$ (say) $\{h''\}_n$ and executes the full work flow

$h''(n) \longrightarrow \chi_n \longrightarrow E(\chi_n) \longrightarrow \mu_n$, plots the pairs (n, μ_n) , and tests for oscillatory behavior using Fourier methods. In other words, the code tests whether or not $\{h''\}_n$ is h -coherent. (The sequences $\{h_n\}_n$ and $\{h'_n\}_n$ are modified to form the sequence $\{h''\}_n$. We set $h_0 = h'_0 = 1/2$, so that $h''_0 = 1$ in conformance with our lemmas.)

Both tables display the relevant significance scores for each plot.

9. TABLES

Supporting data is in SageMath notebooks listed in the index of tables after the bibliography.

1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3

TABLE 1. Residues modulo 4 of abscissas from the lower envelope of Figure 2.

Row	Plot 1	Plot 2	Sum plot
1	Fig. 2B	Fig. 48B	Fig. 50A
2	Fig. 16C	Fig. 17A	Fig. 50B
3	Fig. 2B	Fig. 8C	Fig. 50C
4	Fig. 18B	Fig. 18C	Fig. 50D

TABLE 2. Successful tests for additive closure of V_f . No counterexamples have been detected so far.

Row	Plot 1	Plot 2	Sum plot
1	Fig. 2B	Fig. 48B	Fig. 50A
2	Fig. 16C	Fig. 17A	Fig. 50B

TABLE 3. Successful tests for additive closure of V_h . No counterexamples have been detected so far.

10. FIGURES

Supporting data is in SageMath notebooks listed in the index of figures after the bibliography.

MINIMUM MODULI

FIGURE 1. Minimum moduli for $h(n) = \tau(n)$ with $c = 0$.

FIGURE 2. $c = 1, h(n) = \lambda(n)$

MINIMUM MODULI

LOGS MINIMUM MODULI

FIGURE 3. Minimum moduli and their logarithms for $h(n) = \lambda(n)$ with $c = 2$.

MINIMUM MÓDULI

LOGS MINIMUM MODULI

FIGURE 4. Minimum moduli and their logarithms for $h(n) = \lambda(n)$ with $c = 3$.

FIGURE 5. Minimum moduli over many values of c for $h(n) = \lambda(n)$.

FIGURE 6. Minimum moduli for $h(n) = \tau(p_n + 1)$ with $c = 1$.

MINIMUM MODULI

FIGURE 7. Minimum moduli for $h(n) = \lambda(n)$ before deformation.

FIGURE 8. Cremona curve 11a1.

FIGURE 9. Cremona curve 14a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 10. Cremona curve 15a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 11. Cremona curve 17a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 12. Cremona curve 19a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 13. Cremona curve 20a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 14. Cremona curve 21a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 15. Cremona curve 24a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 16. Cremona curve 26a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 17. Cremona curve 26b1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 18. Cremona curve 27a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 19. Cremona curve 30a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 20. Cremona curve 32a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 21. Cremona curve 33a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 22. Cremona curve 34a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 23. Cremona curve 35a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 24. Cremona curve 36a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 25. Cremona curve 37a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 26. Cremona curve 37b1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 27. Cremona curve 38a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 28. Cremona curve 38b1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 29. Cremona curve 39a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 30. Cremona curve 40a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 31. Cremona curve 42a1 with $c = 1$.

(A) $h(n) = a(n)$.

(B) $h(n) = a(p_n)$.

(C) $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$.

FIGURE 32. Cremona curve 43a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 33. Cremona curve 44a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 34. Cremona curve 45a1 with $c = 1$.

(C) $h(n) = a(p_n + 1)$.FIGURE 35. Cremona curve 46a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 36. Cremona curve 48a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 37. Cremona curve 49a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 38. Cremona curve 50a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 39. Cremona curve 50b1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 40. Cremona curve 51a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 41. Cremona curve 53a1 with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 42. Sum over the unique Galois orbit with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 1, weight 16.

FIGURE 43. Sum over the unique Galois orbit with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 5, weight 4.

FIGURE 44. Sum over the unique Galois orbit with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 5, weight 6.

FIGURE 45. Sum over the unique Galois orbit with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 11, weight 4.

FIGURE 46. Sum over the first of two Galois orbits with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 11, weight 6.

FIGURE 47. Sum over the second of two Galois orbits with $c = 1$ for a cusp form of level 11, weight 6.

FIGURE 48. Prime differences deformed with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 49. $h(n) = n^a, 1 \leq a \leq 4$ with $c = 1$.

FIGURE 50. V_f additive closure tests (minimum moduli for roots of the sums of characteristic polynomials) from Column 3 (“Sum plot”) of Table 2

REFERENCES

- [A22] E. P. Adams, *Smithsonian Mathematical Formulae and Tables of Elliptic Functions*, Smithsonian Institution, Washington, D.C., 1922.
- [Anthropic2026] Anthropic, *Claude Sonnet 4.5, 4.6*, 2026. <https://claude.ai>.
- [Bre24] B. Brent, *Polynomial interpolation of modular forms for Hecke groups*, *Integers*, **21** (#A118) (2021), <https://math.colgate.edu/~integers/v118/v118.pdf>.
- [Bre25] B. Brent, *tau-properties*, GitHub repository, https://github.com/barry314159a/tau_properties, 2025.
- [Bre25a] B. Brent, *Matrix methods for arithmetic functions*, available at <https://arxiv.org/pdf/math/0405083>.
- [cremona] J. E. Cremona, *The Elliptic Curve Database for Conductors to 500000*, available at <https://johncremona.github.io/ecdata/>, 2024, accessed February 2026.
- [diamond-shurman] F. Diamond and J. Shurman, *A First Course in Modular Forms*, Graduate Texts in Mathematics, Vol. 228, Springer, 2005.
- [F] D. Festi, *Notes on Elliptic Curves*, lecture notes, July 22, 2022. Available at https://nesinkoyleri.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/Notes_on_elliptic_curves.pdf.
- [Gh11] M. Gholami, “Division of two power-series by a determinant,” *Int. J. Contemp. Math. Sciences*, vol. 6, no. 15, pp. 735–744, 2011.
- [Go99] H. W. Gould, *The Girard-Waring power sum formulas for symmetric functions, and Fibonacci sequences*, *The Fibonacci Quarterly*, Vol. 37, No. 2 (1999), pp. 135–140, <https://www.fq.math.ca/Scanned/37-2/gould.pdf>.
- [GR88] I. S. Gradshteyn, I. M. Ryzhik, and Robert H. Romer, *Tables of integrals, series, and products*, American Association of Physics Teachers, 1988.
- [HR1918] G. H. Hardy and S. Ramanujan, “Asymptotic formulae in combinatory analysis,” *Proc. Lond. Math. Soc.* (2) **17** (1918), 75–115.
- [Horn2012] Roger A. Horn and Charles R. Johnson, *Matrix Analysis*, Cambridge University Press, 2012.
- [Jameson2016] M. Jameson, J. Thorner, and L. Ye, “Benford’s law for coefficients of newforms,” *International Journal of Number Theory*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 483–494, 2016.
- [Le47] D. H. Lehmer, *The vanishing of Ramanujan’s function $\tau(n)$* , *Duke Math. J.* **14** (1947), 429–433, https://github.com/barry314159a/tau_properties.
- [LMFDB] The LMFDB Collaboration, *The L-functions and Modular Forms Database* howpublished = <https://www.lmfdb.org>, year = 2025
- [M] I. G. Macdonald, *Symmetric Functions and Hall Polynomials*, 2nd ed., Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1995.
- [Marcus] D. A. Marcus, *Number Fields*, 2nd ed., Universitext, Springer, 2018.
- [OEIS] OEIS Foundation Inc. Sequence A000166, Number of permutations of $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ with no fixed points (derangements). *The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences*, 2025. <https://oeis.org/A000166>.
- [Orr] M. Orr, *Algebraic Number Theory*, lecture notes, University of Manchester, 2018–19. Available at <https://personalpages.manchester.ac.uk/staff/Martin.Orr/2018-9/ant/lectures.pdf>.
- [Pe] A. Petojević, *Personal communication*, <https://github.com/barry314159a/public-tau-properties>
- [R2015] S. Ramanujan, *Collected Papers of Srinivasa Ramanujan*, Cambridge University Press, 2015.
- [R] S. Ramanujan, *On certain arithmetical functions*, *Collected Papers of Srinivasa Ramanujan*, AMS Chelsea, 2000.
- [sagemath] The Sage Developers, *SageMath, the Sage Mathematics Software System (Version 10.8)*, 2024, <https://www.sagemath.org>.

- [Si] J. H. Silverman, *The Arithmetic of Elliptic Curves*, Graduate Texts in Mathematics, vol. 106, Springer-Verlag, New York, 1986 (2nd ed. 2009).
- [SloaneA006922] N. J. A. Sloane, *The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences*, published electronically at <https://oeis.org/A006922>, accessed on August 11, 2025.
- [T] H. W. Turnbull, *Theory of Equations*, Oliver and Boyd, Edinburgh and London, 1947, pp. 66–80.
- [Vein1999] Robert Vein and Paul Dale, *Determinants and their Applications in Mathematical Physics*, Springer, 1999, [https://www.nzdr.ru/data/media/biblio/kolxoz/M/MA/MA1/Vein%20R.,%20Dale%20P.%20Determinants%20and%20their%20applications%20in%20mathematical%20physics%20\(p219-220%20scan\)\(Springer,%201998\)\(ISBN%200387985581\)\(0\)\(394s\)_MA1_.pdf](https://www.nzdr.ru/data/media/biblio/kolxoz/M/MA/MA1/Vein%20R.,%20Dale%20P.%20Determinants%20and%20their%20applications%20in%20mathematical%20physics%20(p219-220%20scan)(Springer,%201998)(ISBN%200387985581)(0)(394s)_MA1_.pdf).
- [Wilf2006] H. S. Wilf. *generatingfunctionology*, third edition. A K Peters, Wellesley, MA, 2006. Available at <https://www2.math.upenn.edu/~wilf/DownldGF.html>.
- [1] C. Breuil, B. Conrad, F. Diamond, and R. Taylor. On the modularity of elliptic curves over \mathbb{Q} : wild 3-adic exercises. *Journal of the American Mathematical Society*, 14(4):843–939, 2001. <https://doi.org/10.1090/S0894-0347-01-00370-8>
- [2] B. J. Birch and H. P. F. Swinnerton-Dyer. Notes on elliptic curves. II. *Journal für die reine und angewandte Mathematik*, 218:79–108, 1965. <https://doi.org/10.1515/crll.1965.218.79>
- [3] H. Cohen. *A Course in Computational Algebraic Number Theory*. Graduate Texts in Mathematics, Vol. 138. Springer, 1993. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-02945-9>
- [4] D. A. Cox. *Primes of the Form $x^2 + ny^2$: Fermat, Class Field Theory, and Complex Multiplication*. Wiley, 2nd edition, 2013.
- [5] J. E. Cremona. *Algorithms for Modular Elliptic Curves*. Cambridge University Press, 2nd edition, 1997. Available at <https://homepages.warwick.ac.uk/~masgaj/book/fulltext/>
- [6] J. E. Cremona. *The Elliptic Curve Database for Conductors to 500000*. <https://johncremona.github.io/ecdata/>, 2024.
- [7] D. S. Dummit and R. M. Foote. *Abstract Algebra*. Wiley, 3rd edition, 2004.
- [8] B. H. Gross and D. B. Zagier. Heegner points and derivatives of L-series. *Inventiones mathematicae*, 84(2):225–320, 1986. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01388809>
- [9] B. Mazur. Modular curves and the Eisenstein ideal. *Publications Mathématiques de l’IHÉS*, 47:33–186, 1977. http://www.numdam.org/item/PMIHES_1977__47__33_0/
- [10] L. J. Mordell. On the rational solutions of the indeterminate equations of the third and fourth degrees. *Proceedings of the Cambridge Philosophical Society*, 21:179–192, 1922.
- [11] J-P. Serre. Propriétés galoisiennes des points d’ordre fini des courbes elliptiques. *Inventiones mathematicae*, 15(4):259–331, 1972. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01405086>
- [12] J-P. Serre. *Abelian ℓ -Adic Representations and Elliptic Curves*. A K Peters, 1998. (Originally published 1968)
- [13] J. H. Silverman. *The Arithmetic of Elliptic Curves*. Graduate Texts in Mathematics, Vol. 106. Springer, 2nd edition, 2009. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-09494-6>
- [14] J. H. Silverman. *Advanced Topics in the Arithmetic of Elliptic Curves*. Graduate Texts in Mathematics, Vol. 151. Springer, 1994. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4612-0851-8>
- [15] J. H. Silverman. Computing heights on elliptic curves. *Mathematics of Computation*, 51(183):339–358, 1988. <https://doi.org/10.1090/S0025-5718-1988-0942161-4>
- [16] A. V. Sutherland. Computing images of Galois representations attached to elliptic curves. *Forum of Mathematics, Sigma*, 4:e4, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1017/fms.2015.33>

- [17] R. Taylor and A. Wiles. Ring-theoretic properties of certain Hecke algebras. *Annals of Mathematics*, 141(3):553–572, 1995. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2118560>
- [18] L. C. Washington. *Elliptic Curves: Number Theory and Cryptography*. Chapman & Hall/CRC, 2nd edition, 2008.
- [19] A. Weil. L’arithmétique sur les courbes algébriques. *Acta Mathematica*, 52:281–315, 1929. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02592188>
- [20] A. Wiles. Modular elliptic curves and Fermat’s Last Theorem. *Annals of Mathematics*, 141(3):443–551, 1995. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2118559>

11. APPENDIX 1: INDEX OF FIGURES

The notebooks are in our repository [Bre25].

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Figure 2B	Fig 2B no3 29may26
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12. APPENDIX 2: INDEX OF TABLES

See the following notebooks in our repository [Bre25]. Their file names should be self-explanatory:

12.1. **Table 1.** Notebook:

tauprime=h logarithmic envelopes prec100 n400 1dec25.

12.2. **Table 2.** Notebooks:

Fig 2B no3 29may26

Fig 48B pph c=1 30may26

Fig 2B + Fig 48B charpols 30may26

Fig 16C no3 29may26

Fig 17A no3 27may26

Fig 16C + Fig 17A charpols 30may26

Fig 8C curve 11a1 no3 25may26

Fig 2B + Fig 8C charpols 31may26

Fig 18B + Fig 18C charpols 31may26

12.3. **Table 3.** Notebooks:

$h_{2B} + h_{48B}$ closure 27may26

$h_{16C} + h_{17A}$ closure 28may26

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